

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series : Part XII. Friedel-Crafts Reaction of the Anhydrides of trans-1-Carboxy 3-, and 2-Methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids with Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Synthesis of 2-, and 1-Methyl 8,9- and Substituted 8,9-Benzospiro-(5,5) undecanes

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The anhydrides of trans-1-carboxy 3 and 2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids have been condensed with five aromatic hydrocarbons under the Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions when the corresponding $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'- and 2'-methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids were obtained. Reduction of these furnished the respective $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'- and 2'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -aryl butyric acids, which on cyclisation and subsequent reduction gave 2-, and 1-methyl 8,9- and substituted 8,9-benzo-spiro (5,5) undecanes.

THE work presented in this paper is in continuation of the earlier work¹ and deals with the condensation of the anhydrides (I) of trans-1-carboxy 3-, and 2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids² with benzene, toluene and isomeric xylenes when only one $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'- and 2'-methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids of the type II (X=O) was obtained. The structure of these was established by the formation of pyrylium salts¹, elemental analysis, equivalent weight determination, IR spectral data (1710 and 1690 cm^{-1}); and formation of 2,4-DNPs - further oxidation of these keto-acids furnished the respective aromatic acids identified by m.ps. and mixed m.ps. with authentic samples. Clemmensen reduction of these keto-acids gave the corresponding $\alpha\alpha$ -(3'-, and 2'-methylcyclohexane) γ -arylbutyric acids II (X = H₂); characterisations of II (X = H₂) were also made by the eq. wt. determination, analytical and

and these were characterised through their 2,4-DNPs and IR peaks. These cyclic ketones on modified Clemmensen reduction gave spiro hydrocarbons, 2-, and 1-methyl 8,9- and substituted 8,9-benzo-spiro (5,5) undecanes III (X = H₂).

During the preparations of both the keto- and the reduced acids neutral products of the types described in the earlier communication were obtained.¹

Experimental

A. Anhydride of trans-1-carboxy 3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid.

trans-1-Carboxy 3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (50 g) was refluxed in a R.B. flask (500 ml) with acetic

IR spectral data. Cyclisation of II (X = H₂) with PPA yielded 2-, and 1-methyl-8,9- and substituted 8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5,5) undecanes (III; X = O)

anhydride (100 ml) on a sand bath for 10 hr; excess of acetic anhydride was removed at the pump and the residue fractionated when the pure anhydride distilled at 182-5°/11 mm. n_D^{27} 1.4775. (Yield : 40.0 g; 87.9%).

* For correspondence

α-(3'-Methylcyclohexane)-β-aryloxypropionic acids. A solution of the above anhydride (5.46 g; 0.03 mol) in the dry hydrocarbon (35 ml) contained in a R.B. flask (250 ml) was cooled (-5°), anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.8 g; 0.066 mol) gradually added during 1 hr with constant shaking, the contents kept in an ice-salt bath for 4 hr and left at room temperature for 24 hr. The reaction mixture after heating in an oil bath (50°-60°) for 3 hr was worked up in the customary manner and the product purified by refluxing with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%; 400 ml) and subsequent acidification. Crystallisation from benzene-pet. ether (60°-80°) gave the corresponding *α*-(3'-methylcyclohexane)-β-aryloxypropionic acids, which are entered in Table 1A.

α-(3'-Methylcyclohexane)-γ-butyric acids. *α*-(3'-Methylcyclohexane)-β-aryloxypropionic acids (5.2 g) were reduced by Clemmensen method employing amalgamated zinc (50 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (100 ml) and refluxing for 50-60 hr with

the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) every 5 hr. The reaction mixture on working up in the customary manner yielded *α*-(3'-methylcyclohexane)-γ-butyric acids given in Table 2A.

2-Methyl 8,9- and substituted 8,9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5,5) undecanes were obtained by the cyclisation of *α*-(3'-methylcyclohexane)-γ-butyric acids (2.46 g) with PPA (phosphorus pentoxide, 15 g and ortho phosphoric acid, 10 ml) which were purified by distillation in vacuum and these are entered in Table 3A.

2-Methyl 8,9- and substituted 8,9-benzo-spiro (5,5) undecanes were prepared by the modified Clemmensen reduction of the above spiro-ketones (1.14 g) using amalgamated zinc (65 g), concentrated hydrochloric acid (125 ml.), toluene (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and refluxing for 65 hrs with the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) every 5 hr. The spiro hydrocarbons were purified by distillation in vacuum and are given in Table 4A.

TABLE 1A
α-(3'-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE) β-AROXYLPROPIONIC ACIDS

AROYL	M.P./b.p. °C	Yield %	Found eq. wt. monobasic	Molecular formula	Analysis				2,4-DNP °C
					Found%		Requires%		
					C	H	C	H	
1. Benzoyl	177	83.3	260.2	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃	73.6	7.5	73.8	7.7	141
2. 4-Methylbenzoyl	179	86.4	274.2	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₃	74.2	8.1	74.5	8.0	162
3. 3,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	140	81.0	287.9	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₃	74.8	8.2	75.0	8.3	211-2
4. 2,4- " "	175	75.3	287.8	"	74.9	8.4	"	"	156
5. 2,5- " "	211-5/6 mm	72.6	288.0	"	74.9	8.3	"	"	126

TABLE 2A
α-(3'-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE)-γ-ARYL BUTYRIC ACIDS

ARYL	B.P. °C	Yield %	Refractive index	Found eq. wt. monobasic	Molecular formula	Analysis			
						Found%		Requires%	
						C	H	C	H
1 Phenyl	215-20/9.5mm	85.4	<i>n</i> _D ^{20.5} 1.5320	246.0	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂	78.2	8.8	78.0	8.9
2. 4-Methylphenyl	200-3/5 mm	82.0	<i>n</i> _D ^{20.5} 1.5315	260.0	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₂	78.2	9.2	78.5	9.2
3. 3,4-Dimethylphenyl	210-5/9.5mm	80.3	<i>n</i> _D ²⁰ 1.5355	273.6	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₂	78.6	9.4	78.8	9.5
4. 2,4- " "	165-8/9 mm	76.7	<i>n</i> _D ²⁶ 1.5395	273.8	"	78.8	9.6	"	"
5. 2,5- " "	212-5/8 mm	77.6	<i>n</i> _D ^{20.5} 1.5475	274.0	"	78.6	9.4	"	"

TABLE 3A
2-METHYL 8,9- AND SUBSTITUTED 8,9-BENZO-10-KETO SPIRO-(5,5) UNDECANES

Substituents in the benzene ring	B.P. °C	Yield %	Refractive index	Molecular formula	Analysis				2,4-DNP m.p.°C
					Found%		Requires%		
					C	H	C	H	
1. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	115/8 mm	74.5	<i>n</i> _D ^{20.5} 1.5605	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O	84.0	8.7	84.0	8.8	205
2. R ₁ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H; R ₂ =CH ₃	165-7/9.5mm	74.3	<i>n</i> _D ^{20.5} 1.5675	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O	84.2	9.0	84.3	9.1	276
3. R ₁ =R ₄ =H; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃	160-2/8.5mm	74.2	<i>n</i> _D ²⁶ 1.5570	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O	84.2	9.3	84.4	9.4	225
4. R ₁ =R ₃ =H; R ₂ =R ₄ =CH ₃	178-80/2 mm	78.1	<i>n</i> _D ²⁷ 1.5465	"	84.2	9.5	"	"	158
5. R ₂ =R ₃ =H; R ₁ =R ₄ =CH ₃	163-8/9 mm	72.2	<i>n</i> _D ²⁷ 1.5550	"	84.2	9.3	"	"	139

TABLE 4A

2-METHYL 8,9-AND SUBSTITUTED-8,9-BENZO-SPIRO-(5,5) UNDECANES

Substituents in the benzene ring	B.P. °C	Yield %	Refractive index	Molecular formula	Analysis			
					Found%		Requires%	
					C	H	C	H
1. $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$	150-2/2.5mm	79.4	n_D^{29} 1.5285	$C_{16}H_{22}$	89.5	10.2	89.7	10.3
2. $R_1=R_3=R_4=H$; $R_2=CH_3$	138-9/5 mm	74.0	n_D^{29} 1.5460	$C_{17}H_{24}$	89.3	10.6	89.5	10.5
3. $R_1=R_4=H$; $R_2=R_3=CH_3$	155-7/10.5mm	78.5	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5485	$C_{18}H_{26}$	89.2	10.6	89.3	10.7
4. $R_1=R_3=H$; $R_2=R_4=CH_3$	152-4/10 mm	78.5	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5340	"	89.2	10.5	"	"
5. $R_2=R_3=H$; $R_1=R_4=CH_3$	156/9 mm	66.1	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5430	"	89.3	10.6	"	"

B. Anhydride of *trans*-1-carboxy 2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid: M.p. 171°, was prepared by refluxing the acid (50 g) with acetic anhydride (100 ml) for 10 hr, removing the excess of acetic anhydride under vacuum and distilling the residue

at 175°/15 mm. n_D^{27} 1.4810. (Yield: 40.5 g; 89.0%).

α -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- β -aroyl propionic acids were prepared by the reaction of the above anhydride (6.0 g; 0.033 mol) with the aromatic hydrocarbons

TABLE 1B

 α -(2'-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE)- β -AROYL PROPIONIC ACIDS

AROYL	M.P. °C	Yield %	Found eq. wt. monobasic	Molecular formula	Analysis				2,4-DNP °C
					Found%		Requires%		
					C	H	C	H	
1. Benzoyl	144	93.2	260.0	$C_{16}H_{20}O_3$	73.6	7.7	73.8	7.7	134
2. 4-Methylbenzoyl	136	88.4	274.0	$C_{17}H_{22}O_3$	74.3	8.0	74.5	8.0	130
3. 3,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	168	73.7	287.6	$C_{18}H_{24}O_3$	74.9	8.1	75.0	8.3	146
4. 2,4- " "	152	80.5	287.8	"	74.9	8.2	"	"	133
5. 2,5- " "	134	80.0	287.9	"	74.9	8.3	"	"	249

TABLE 2B

 α -(2'-METHYLCYCLOHEXANE)- γ -ARYL BUTYRIC ACIDS

ARYL	M.P./b.p. °C	Yield %	Found eq. wt. monobasic	Molecular formula	Analysis			
					Found%		Requires%	
					C	H	C	H
1. Phenyl	m.p. 105 (b.p. 175-6/6 mm)	71.1	246.0	$C_{16}H_{22}O_2$	77.9	8.7	78.0	8.0
2. 4-Methylphenyl	131	35.2	260.0	$C_{17}H_{24}O_2$	78.4	9.1	78.5	9.2
3. 3,4-Dimethylphenyl	m.p. 145 (b.p. 190/10 mm)	61.1	273.6	$C_{18}H_{26}O_2$	78.6	9.4	78.8	9.5
4. 2,4- " "	m.p. 132 (b.p. 200-4/4 mm)	63.9	273.8	"	78.7	9.6	"	"
5. 2,5- " "	m.p. 125 (b.p. 210/4 mm)	64.0	273.8	"	78.8	9.3	"	"

TABLE 3B

1-METHYL 8,9-AND SUBSTITUTED 8,9-BENZO-10-KETO-SPIRO (5,5) UNDECANES

Substituents in the benzene ring	B.P. °C	Yield %	Ref. index	Molecular formula	Analysis				2,4-DNP °C
					Found%		Requires%		
					C	H	C	H	
1. $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$	158-9/6 mm	65.8	n_D^{31} 1.5642	$C_{16}H_{20}O$	84.1	8.9	84.2	8.8	157
2. $R_1=R_3=R_4=H$; $R_2=CH_3$	176-7/6.5 mm	62.0	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5570	$C_{17}H_{22}O$	84.3	9.0	84.3	9.1	147
3. $R_1=R_4=H$; $R_2=R_3=CH_3$	165/13 mm	60.5	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.6030	$C_{18}H_{24}O$	84.1	9.3	84.4	9.4	141
4. $R_1=R_3=H$; $R_2=R_4=CH_3$	190/5.5 mm	60.5	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5585	"	84.2	9.4	"	"	192
5. $R_2=R_3=H$; $R_1=R_4=CH_3$	198-200/5.5mm	82.0	$n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5572	"	84.1	9.2	"	"	161

TABLE 4B

1-METHYL 8,9 AND SUBSTITUTED 8,9-BENZO-SPIRO (5,5) UNDECANES

Substituents in the benzene ring	B.P. °C	Yield %	Ref. index	Molecular formula	Analysis			
					Found %		Requires %	
					C	H	C	H
1. R ₁ = R ₂ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H	130/4 mm	60.7	n _D ^{29.5} 1.5452	C ₁₆ H ₂₂	89.5	10.2	89.7	10.3
2. R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H; R ₂ = CH ₃	140/8 mm	61.9	n _D ^{29.5} 1.5410	C ₁₇ H ₂₄	89.4	10.4	89.5	10.5
3. R ₁ = R ₄ = H; R ₂ = R ₃ = CH ₃	165/5 mm	53.7	n _D ^{30.5} 1.5682	C ₁₈ H ₂₆	89.2	10.4	89.3	10.7
4. R ₁ = R ₃ = H; R ₂ = R ₄ = CH ₃	170/5 mm	58.0	n _D ^{29.5} 1.5420	„	89.2	10.4	89.3	10.7
5. R ₂ = R ₃ = H; R ₁ = R ₄ = CH ₃	170-2/4mm	82.6	n _D ^{29.5} 1.5395	„	89.1	10.4	„	„

(35 ml) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (9.7 g; 0.072 mol) and working up in the manner described under A above. The different keto-acids which were purified by crystallisation are entered in Table 1B.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-Methylcyclohexane)- γ -butyric acids were obtained by Clemmensen reduction of $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- β -aroylpropionic acids (5.2 g) following the procedure given under A above and these are entered in Table 2B.

1-Methyl 8,9- and substituted-8,9 benzo-10-keto spiro (5,5)-undecanes were prepared by the cyclisation of $\alpha\alpha$ -(2'-methylcyclohexane)- γ -arylbutyric acids (2.46 g)

with PPA (phosphorous pentoxide, 15 g and ortho-phosphoric acid, 10 ml), purified by distillation under vacuum and are entered in Table 3B.

1-Methyl 8,9- and substituted 8,9-benzo spiro (5,5) undecanes were obtained by reducing the above spiro-ketones (1.14 g) by modified Clemmensen method and working up in the normal manner and these are given in Table 4B.

References

1. H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 203.
2. H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (Communicated).